

Wrist Accelerometry-based Digital Assessment of Slowness of Movement in Parkinson’s Disease: a Multi-Cohort Analysis

Ioannis Gerasimou¹, Apostolos Moustaklis¹, Charalampos Sotirakis¹, Stelios Hadjidimitriou¹
and Leontios J. Hadjileontiadis^{2,1}

Abstract—Bradykinesia and rigidity are two of the core motor symptoms of Parkinsonism. Current clinical assessment is confined into in-person clinical setting, involves the element of subjectivity and does not take day-to-day fluctuations into account. Wearable sensor accelerometer data offer the potential for objective and continuous monitoring of motor symptoms. This work aimed to build upon previous knowledge on the utility of wrist accelerometer-based digital biomarker (dBM) of gross upper limb motor impairment. Data from two cohorts captured in a daily-living setting were used: the Verily Study Watch of Parkinson’s Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) for model training and the Michael J. Fox Foundation (MJFF) Levodopa Response Study for external evaluation. First, a hand movement detector and a gait detector were developed to isolate periods of hand movement without walking. Then, using the accelerometer raw signals from these periods, a slowness of movement estimator was trained to produce a digital severity score, using as ground truth a composite severity score derived from the MDS-UPDRS Part III items relevant to bradykinesia and rigidity. The slowness of movement estimator demonstrated moderate to strong correlation ($r = 0.66, p < 0.05$) with the respective clinical score, and was able to discriminate between symptom severity groups ($p < 0.01$). External evaluation with sensor data from two wrist-worn devices confirmed the model’s generalizability through comparable correlation strengths ($r > 0.60, p < 0.05$). Our work extends and provides evidence of robustness regarding a dBM that could be utilized to unobtrusively monitor upper limb slowness of movement in a daily living setting using only accelerometer data from a wrist-worn device.

Clinical relevance— This analysis underlines the prospects of wrist-worn accelerometer sensors to provide an unobtrusive, cost-effective, accessible and objective measurement of aspects of upper limb motor impairment by continuous monitoring in a daily-living setting.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson’s disease (PD) is a complex neurodegenerative disorder affecting millions of people globally each year. Rigidity and bradykinesia are cardinal PD motor symptoms that significantly affect the person’s mobility and consequently their quality of life. Along with tremor, they form a collection of symptoms referred to as Parkinsonism, which constitutes the core clinical diagnostic criteria for PD [1].

The heterogeneity and day-to-day fluctuations of PD symptom manifestation add challenges to clinical monitoring

I. Gerasimou and A. Moustaklis are co-first authors. I. Gerasimou is the corresponding author (email: gerasimoi@auth.gr).

¹Dpt. of Electrical & Computer Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

²Department of Biomedical Engineering and Biotechnology, Khalifa University, Abu Dhabi, UAE

and may impede timely and accurate diagnosis. Additionally, the current gold standard clinical examination for PD diagnosis, the Movement Disorder Society – Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) depends on the clinical examiner’s subjectivity [2]. Accurate and timely diagnosis of PD associated symptoms, such as rigidity and bradykinesia, could benefit people with PD (PwPD) by allowing better disease management and treatment.

The emergence and accessibility of wearable sensors present a viable approach by enabling the continuous symptom monitoring for PwPD. Unsupervised active tests using wearable sensors can accurately track PD related motor symptoms [3]. However, data collection protocols should be designed to minimize the burden on participants. Working towards this direction, Mahadevan et al. [4], have shown that wearable accelerometers can objectively quantify PD-related upper limb motor symptoms in activities of daily-living highlighting its potential in assessing rigidity and bradykinesia unobtrusively. These advances indicate that wearable sensor data can contribute in assessing the effectiveness of symptom-targeting treatment in PD [5].

The aim of this work was to develop and validate a wrist accelerometer-based dBM to facilitate the continuous monitoring of gross upper limb slowness of movement in a daily-living setting by developing a digital bradykinesia and rigidity score derived from a combination of the MDS-UPDRS Part III relevant items. Using accelerometer data captured in a passive setting during daily-living, we trained and internally tested the dBM on the Verily Study Watch dataset [6] and externally tested its generalizability capability with two wrist-worn devices from the MJFF Levodopa Response study dataset [7].

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

A. Datasets

To train the slowness of movement estimator we used the raw accelerometer signal data from the Verily Study Watch dataset available through the Parkinson’s Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) [6]. PPMI collected data from PwPD, persons at risk of developing PD and Healthy Controls (HC) using the Verily Study Watch (Verily Life Sciences LLC, Dallas, TX) wrist-worn device. On average 485 ± 212 days of accelerometer data of nominal sampling rate 100Hz along with 2.29 ± 1.26 MDS-UPDRS Part III assessments were available for every participant. For this analysis we included only the PwPD ($n = 143$), persons at risk ($n = 135$) and HC ($n = 32$) who had at least one

TABLE I
DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PPMI VERILY STUDY WATCH PARTICIPANTS INCLUDED IN THE ANALYSIS

Characteristics	PD	Persons at risk	Healthy Controls
n (total n = 310)	143	135	32
Demographics			
Females	57	87	14
Males	86	48	18
Age (std)	62.06 (8.77)	61.29 (6.94)	58.63 (11.71)
Clinical characteristics			
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	5.83 (2.37)	N.A.	N.A.
Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III score (std)	22.66 (9.83)	2.49 (3.63)	1.03 (1.80)

TABLE II
DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MJFF LEVODOPA RESPONSE STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Characteristics	PD
n	16
Demographics	
Females	4
Males	12
Age (std)	64.62(7.83)
Clinical characteristics	
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	9.27 (3.75)
Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III score (std)	44.25 (12.05)

MDS-UPDRS Part III assessment ($n = 533$) while being under antiparkinsonian medication (ON state). Six days of accelerometer data that followed a clinical assessment were included in the analysis. Table I contains the key sample clinico-demographic characteristics.

The Michael J. Fox Foundation (MJFF) Levodopa Response Study dataset [7] was used to externally validate the slowness of movement assessment pipeline trained on the Verily Study Watch dataset. Data were collected from PwPD using two different smartwatches, a GENEActiv (Activinsights Inc., Kimbolton, United Kingdom) and a Pebble (Pebble Technology Corporation, Palo Alto, CA), worn on the most and least affected upper limb, respectively. Four days of accelerometer data of nominal sampling rate $50Hz$ are available for each participant along with 2 MDS-UPDRS Part III assessments conducted on Day 1 and Day 4. On Day 1, patients were assessed after taking antiparkinsonian medication (ON state), while on Day 4, they were instructed to refrain from taking their regular medication (OFF state). Table II summarizes the key clinico-demographic characteristics.

A third dataset, Capture-24 dataset [8], was used to develop a gait detector in order to identify and omit periods of gait activity, prior to slowness of movement detection. Capture-24 contains data from $n = 151$ participants.

B. Slowness of Movement Assessment Pipeline

The slowness of movement assessment pipeline (Fig. 1) extended the work originally proposed by Mahadevan et al. [4]. The process included three high-level sequential steps: a hand movement detection, a gait detection and a slowness of movement estimation. The hand movement detector, working in conjunction with the gait detector, isolated hand

movements not related to the natural arm swing that occurs during walking. A preprocessed 5-second 3-axis accelerometer segment was fed into a hand movement detector. If hand movement was detected, the segment proceeded to the gait detector. If gait was not detected, the segment was marked with a non-gait label. As illustrated by Fig. 2, each 6 consecutive 5-second segments forming a 30-s window underwent majority voting to determine the most frequent label. All eligible 5-second segments within a 30-s window marked with a "Hand movement and non-gait" label were aggregated for each 10-minute period and processed by the slowness of movement estimator, which then calculated a numerical score indicative of the severity of slowness of movement.

C. Data pre-processing

Each 3-axis accelerometer signal was segmented into continuous non-overlapping 5-second windows and resampled at 25 Hz. This sampling rate was chosen as sufficient for human activities recognition, because it ensures compatibility with commercially available smartwatches, typically operating at lower sampling rates to conserve battery power [9], [10]. Any emerging empty windows due to gaps greater than 5-seconds were discarded.

D. Hand Movement Detector

The heuristic method proposed by Mahadevan et al. [4] is used to detect hand movement. For each 5-s segment, the signal vector magnitude ($\sqrt{a_x^2 + a_y^2 + a_z^2}$) was computed to eliminate the dependence on device orientation. Then, the magnitude was filtered using a 6th-order low-pass Butterworth filter with a cut-off frequency of 3 Hz to reduce noise associated to tremor and a rolling coefficient of variation ($c_v = \frac{\mu}{\sigma}$, where μ was the mean and σ the standard deviation) was calculated by sliding a 1-second window. The 1-second window was considered to contain hand movement if the coefficient was $c_v > 0.01$. The five consecutive 1-second windows were combined into a 5-second window, and the final label (hand movement or no hand movement) was determined by the majority of the 1-second window labels.

E. Gait Detector

A magnitude-based model was developed to rely solely on signal vector magnitude-related features extracted from

Fig. 1. Overview of the pipeline used from the slowness of movement assessment from wrist accelerometer.

the 3-axis accelerometer signal, such as magnitude’s higher-order statistics, signal autocorrelation and dominant frequency. The labeled accelerometer data of the Capture-24 dataset were used for training the gait detection model. A LightGBM classifier was employed with a nested cross-validation scheme to evaluate performance and perform hyperparameter tuning. For the outer fold of the nested cross-validation, a Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) scheme was applied, while for the inner fold a 5-fold approach. Our gait detector achieved an average performance of AUC 0.79 (95 % CI [0.77, 0.80]). By conducting a ROC analysis, a prediction threshold of 0.7 was selected to maximize specificity (Spec.=0.97) and optimize the performance on the true negative predictions (non-gait label).

In the pipeline, for each 5-second window that hand movement was detected, the signal was band-passed filtered (4th order, Butterworth filter) in the range of $[0.25 - 3.00] Hz$ to isolate the frequency band associated with walking. Subsequently, feature extraction was performed to classify the segment as a gait or non-gait period.

F. Slowness of Movement Estimator

Slowness of movement was estimated in 10-minute intervals. The features of Table III were extracted from the signal vector of eligible 5-s segments within a 30-s non-gait hand movement window and aggregated over the 10-minute interval by calculating standard deviation, median and the 75th percentile values for x, y, z, and magnitude. As a result, the estimator receives the aggregation of a cluster of 5-s segments with hand movement and lack of gait. This was done to minimize the effect of possible misclassifications in the hand movement and gait detectors.

TABLE III

FEATURES EXTRACTED IN EACH 5-S WINDOW FOR THE SLOWNESS OF MOVEMENT ESTIMATOR

Feature Name	Description
Root mean square	Root mean square (RMS) of the vector
Smoothness	Scaled mean squared jerk of the vector [11]
Peak Acceleration	Maximum absolute value of the vector
Range of Motion	Max - Min of the vector
Signal Entropy	Shannon entropy

To develop a score indicative of the severity of slowness of movement, using the feature vectors of 10-minute intervals, we trained a regressor to estimate a slowness of movement composite score (range $[0 - 12]$) as the sum of MDS-UPDRS Part III: a) averaged (left and right) upper limb rigidity

Fig. 2. Time-wise classification of hand movement and gait presence over a 10-min period of slowness of movement estimation. Slowness of movement features are extracted only for 5-s windows classified as having hand movement and absence of gait in 30-s valid intervals (with hand movement and absence of gait based on majority voting on classifications of constituent 5-s windows).

item scores (items 3.3b, 3.3c), b) averaged hand pronation-supination item scores (items 3.6a, 3.6b), and c) global spontaneity of movement item score (item 3.14). All items were measured in the ON state. The average upper limb scores were used because the Verily Study Watch dataset lacked information on the wrist on which the participants wore the watch. The UPDRS part III items were selected based on their likelihood of affecting gross upper limb functionality and the capability of the wrist accelerometer to detect these movements.

G. Training & Internal Validation

The composite score was extracted from each Verily MDS-UPDRS Part III assessment for PwPD (3.67 ± 1.75), HC (0.27 ± 0.45) and persons at risk (0.45 ± 0.92) and was paired with the features extracted from up to six days after each assessment. LightGBM regressors were selected due to their lightweight nature to be trained and tested under a nested cross-validation scheme. For the outer fold a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) scheme was used by leaving out all features and MDS-UPDRS assessments associated to a participant. For the inner fold Optuna [12] was used for hyper parameter tuning by conducting 5 trials of a 5-fold scheme. In each trial, the hyperparameters were optimized by Optuna with Bayesian optimization by maximizing the R^2 and minimizing the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). The LightGBM regressor was then instantiated with the optimal hyperparameters from the best trial and trained on the entire training set of the respective LOSO outer fold.

The final digital score was calculated in two steps: first, the mean of all predictions for the 10-minute intervals within each day was computed, resulting in six daily means. Then, these six daily means were averaged to obtain the final digital score. Spearman’s rank correlation was used to evaluate the association of the estimated digital scores of slowness of movement of testing subjects with the respective composite clinical score. To further assess the dBMs’ diagnostic value, pairwise comparisons were performed using the Mann-Whitney-U test with Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons, across four emerging symptom severity groups (Composite clinical score: [0], [1-3], [3-5], [5-8]).

H. External Validation

We externally validated our slowness of movement assessment pipeline using the MJFF Levodopa Response study dataset. The slowness of movement estimator model used in the external validation was trained on the complete Verily Study Watch dataset, with hyperparameters optimized using Optuna, following the same approach as in the inner loop of the internal testing. Two separate validations were performed for participants’ most and least affected upper limb using signals from GENEActiv and Pebble, respectively. A limb-specific composite score was used as the ground truth, as for this dataset the information regarding the placement of each device on either wrist was available. For the smartwatches worn on the left wrist we used the sum of the items 3.3c, 3.6b and 3.14, while for those on the right wrist the sum of the items 3.3b, 3.6a and 3.14. To match the distribution of symptom fluctuations that the slowness of movement estimator model was trained on, the MDS-UPDRS Part III assessment items measured during Day 1 were used, when participants were under antiparkinsonian medication (ON state). Participants with a decreased composite score during assessment in the OFF state (Day 4) compared to the assessment during the ON state (Day 1) were excluded, due to not responding as expected to the antiparkinsonian medication. A participant wearing the GENEActiv on their lower limbs was also excluded from the analysis. As a result of this filtering process, the number of eligible participants for analysis differs between the two devices (GENEActive $n = 13$ / Pebble $n = 11$).

III. RESULTS

The Spearman’s rank correlation results obtained during the internal validation are depicted in Fig. 3. Moderate to strong associations ($r = 0.66$, $p < 0.05$) were observed between the digital slowness of movement score and the composite score labels of the Verily Study Watch dataset. Results from comparisons performed across the four symptom severity groups are shown in Fig.4. Pairwise comparisons show that digital scores differ significantly between all severity groups (0 vs [1-3]: $p = 5.711 \times 10^{-14}$, $U = 8.120 \times 10^3$, [1-3] vs [3-5]: $p = 1.229 \times 10^{-8}$, $U = 2.996 \times 10^3$, [3-5] vs [5-8]: $p = 5.328 \times 10^{-3}$, $U = 1.790 \times 10^3$) revealing the models utility in discriminating among the different severity levels.

The external validation on the MJFF Levodopa Response study data showed that the predicted digital composite score obtained from the most affected limb exhibited a moderate to strong correlation ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.05$) with the slowness of movement composite score labels (Fig. 5a). Comparably, for the signals obtained from the least affected limb, a strong correlation ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.05$) was observed between the digital and the clinical scores (Fig. 5b).

Fig. 3. Association between the clinical composite slowness of movement score and the digital slowness of movement score predicted by the pipeline on the accelerometer signals of the Verily Study Watch.

Fig. 4. Distributions of the estimated digital scores grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$, ** $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$.

IV. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study was to implement and validate a dBM tracking aspects of upper limb motor impairment using a wrist accelerometer during daily living. Accurate tracking of motor symptoms using low-cost devices and machine learning algorithms could benefit clinical experts

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Association between the clinical composite slowness of movement score and the digital slowness of movement score predicted by the pipeline for the accelerometer signals of (a) the most affected limb (GENEActiv) and (b) the least affected limb (Pebble).

to accurately screen, diagnose, and timely treat disease-related symptoms by using these tools either independently or integrated into prognostic and diagnostic models [13] as components of continuous monitoring systems. The results indicate that wrist accelerometer data can be used to accurately capture clinical signs of slowness of movement in a passive setting, providing a robust indicator of PD-related motor symptom severity.

The results of this study are in line with previous studies showing that continuous sensor measurement can capture the severity of PD related motor symptoms [4]. The clinical utility of the dBM was further evidenced by a medium to strong association between the model predictions and the clinical scores (MDS-UPDRS part III items). Importantly, the model demonstrated discriminatory value as it confirmed differences among different symptom severity levels.

To ensure robustness and generalizability of the developed dBM, the model outcomes were evaluated against an independent dataset. This external dataset was selected to include wrist accelerometer data collected during daily living by different individuals using different devices. The outcomes of this evaluation step indicate that the developed pipeline can provide equally accurate results across diverse wrist-worn sensors.

The results of this study need to be interpreted with caution for several reasons. First, the impact of key socio-demographics, medical history and medication effects has not been investigated. At this stage, analysis focused on the utility of the free-living acceleration signal alone. Second, although the present study used three independent datasets to train and evaluate its outcomes, in order to develop robust diagnostic and prognostic models more data from diverse populations are required. The small sample size of the external dataset hindered the ability to evaluate the pipeline's discriminatory performance for symptom severity on the external dataset. Third, only four days of accelerometer data were available in the independent dataset, therefore limiting the ability to evaluate longitudinal symptom tracking. Fourth, the lack of information regarding the side at which the accelerometer was worn, did not allow for a more thorough analysis, respecting the unilateral nature of PD.

For future work, we aim to apply and further validate the proposed pipeline using a more diverse dataset and examine its efficacy for longitudinal symptom tracking during daily-living.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work is part of the AI-PROGNOSIS project funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101080581. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Health and Digital Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

The Levodopa Response study was funded by the Michael J Fox Foundation. Data were obtained from the Synapse (<https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn20681023>) by filing a formal request.

Data used in the preparation of this article were obtained on [2023-11-23] from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) database (www.ppmi-info.org/access-data-specimens/download-data), RRID:SCR.006431. For up-to-date information on the study, visit www.ppmi-info.org

PPMI – a public-private partnership – is funded by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research and funding partners, including 4D Pharma, Abbvie, AcureX, Allergan, Amathus Therapeutics, Aligning Science Across Parkinson's, AskBio, Avid Radiopharmaceuticals, BIAL, BioArctic, Biogen, Biohaven, BioLegend, BlueRock Therapeutics, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Calico Labs, Capsida Biotherapeutics, Celgene, Cerevel Therapeutics, Coave Ther-

apeutics, DaCapo Brainscience, Denali, Edmond J. Safra Foundation, Eli Lilly, Gain Therapeutics, GE HealthCare, Genentech, GSK, Golub Capital, Handl Therapeutics, In-sitro, Jazz Pharmaceuticals, Johnson & Johnson Innovative Medicine, Lundbeck, Merck, Meso Scale Discovery, Mission Therapeutics, Neurocrine Biosciences, Neuron23, Neurope, Pfizer, Piramal, Prevail Therapeutics, Roche, Sanofi, Servier, Sun Pharma Advanced Research Company, Takeda, Teva, UCB, Vanqua Bio, Verily, Voyager Therapeutics, the Weston Family Foundation and Yumanity Therapeutics.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. B. Postuma, D. Berg, M. Stern, W. Poewe, C. W. Olanow, W. Oertel *et al.*, “MDS clinical diagnostic criteria for Parkinson’s disease,” *Movement Disorders*, vol. 30, no. 12, pp. 1591–1601, 2015.
- [2] J. J. FitzGerald, Z. Lu, P. Jareonsettasin, and C. A. Antoniadis, “Quantifying Motor Impairment in Movement Disorders,” *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 12, p. 202, Apr. 2018.
- [3] G. Oyama, M. Burq, T. Hatano, W. J. Marks, R. Kapur, J. Fernandez *et al.*, “Analytical and clinical validity of wearable, multi-sensor technology for assessment of motor function in patients with Parkinson’s disease in Japan,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 3600, Mar. 2023.
- [4] N. Mahadevan, C. Demanuele, H. Zhang, D. Volfson, B. Ho, M. K. Erb *et al.*, “Development of digital biomarkers for resting tremor and bradykinesia using a wrist-worn wearable device,” *npj Digital Medicine*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 5, Jan. 2020.
- [5] N. Shawen, M. K. O’Brien, S. Venkatesan, L. Lonini, T. Simuni, J. L. Hamilton, R. Ghaffari, J. A. Rogers, and A. Jayaraman, “Role of data measurement characteristics in the accurate detection of Parkinson’s disease symptoms using wearable sensors,” *Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 52, Apr. 2020.
- [6] K. Marek, D. Jennings, S. Lasch, A. Siderowf, C. Tanner, T. Simuni *et al.*, “The parkinson progression marker initiative (ppmi),” *Progress in Neurobiology*, vol. 95, no. 4, p. 629–635, Dec. 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pneurobio.2011.09.005>
- [7] J.-F. Daneault, G. Vergara-Diaz, F. Parisi, C. Admati, C. Alfonso, M. Bertoli *et al.*, “Accelerometer data collected with a minimum set of wearable sensors from subjects with Parkinson’s disease,” *Scientific Data*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 48, Feb. 2021.
- [8] S. Chan, Y. Hang, C. Tong, A. Acquah, A. Schonfeldt, J. Gershuny *et al.*, “CAPTURE-24: A large dataset of wrist-worn activity tracker data collected in the wild for human activity recognition,” *Scientific Data*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 1135, Oct. 2024.
- [9] A. Tsanas, “Investigating Wrist-Based Acceleration Summary Measures across Different Sample Rates towards 24-Hour Physical Activity and Sleep Profile Assessment,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 16, p. 6152, Jan. 2022.
- [10] A. Khan, N. Hammerla, S. Mellor, and T. Plötz, “Optimising sampling rates for accelerometer-based human activity recognition,” *Pattern Recognition Letters*, vol. 73, pp. 33–40, Apr. 2016.
- [11] N. Hogan and D. Sternad, “Sensitivity of Smoothness Measures to Movement Duration, Amplitude, and Arrests,” *Journal of Motor Behavior*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 529–534, Nov. 2009.
- [12] T. Akiba, S. Sano, T. Yanase, T. Ohta, and M. Koyama, “Optuna: A next-generation hyperparameter optimization framework,” in *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2019.
- [13] P. Rábano-Suárez, N. Del Campo, I. Benatru, C. Moreau, C. Desjardins, Á. Sánchez-Ferro, and M. Fabbri, “Digital Outcomes as Biomarkers of Disease Progression in Early Parkinson’s Disease: A Systematic Review,” *Movement Disorders*, p. mds.30056, Nov. 2024.